

Table 3. Effect of laser treatments on panicle characteristics of rice. GuangZhou, China, 1980.

Treatment	Panicle characteristics ^a				
	Primary rachis-branches (no.)	Secondary rachis-branches (no.)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Fertile (%)	1,000 grain wt (g)
	<i>Zhen-Zhu-Ai</i>				
Control	9.7	14.1	88.0	88.8	23.7
He-Ne laser	11.0	15.9	107.8	89.8	23.6
Ar ⁺ laser	11.0	15.8	101.4	96.6	24.6
N ₂ laser	9.3	18.8	110.2	90.0	25.0
	<i>Zhai- Ye-Qing</i>				
Control	10.5	14.6	89.7	86.4	23.0
He-N laser	9.8	16.6	95.0	89.1	25.1
Ar ⁺ laser	10.0	15.5	102.0	91.5	25.1
N ₂ laser	9.0	15.0	18.8	88.1	25.4

^aMean of 20 panicles inspected. For the laser treatment, germinated seeds were planted in pots and placed in the field garden.

Table 4. Effect of CO₂-laser treatment on panicle characteristics of rice, Guangzhou, China, 1980.

Treatment	Panicle characteristic ^a				
	Primary rachis-branches (no.)	Secondary rachis-branches (no.)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Fertile (%)	1,000 grain wt (g)
	<i>Zhen-Zhu-Ai</i>				
Control	10.1	18.7	87.4	76.5	21.6
CO ₂ laser	12.1	18.4	124.4	91.8	23.7
	<i>Zhai- Ye-Qing</i>				
Control	8.8	15.6	70.2	12.1	21.6
CO ₂ laser	9.0	15.4	85.8	90.1	23.2

^aMean of 20 panicles inspected.

efficiency of the N₂ laser treatment differs with variety and with seed status.

CO₂ laser treatment of Zhen-Zhu-Ai increased its 1,000-grain weight about 19.0% and number of filled grains by 18.2-37.0 grains/panicle (Table 4). For Zhai-Ye-Qing, CO₂ laser treatment

increased the 1,000-grain weight by 5.5% and the number of filled grains by 15.5-15.8 grains/panicle, and delayed panicle emergence by 2-3 days.

Seed treatment with all four lasers slightly decreased the protein content of rough rice. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Evaluation of new technology developed at Walagambahuwa Minor Tank Settlement in Sri Lanka

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The Walagambahuwa settlement is typical of 10,000 similar settlements with 100-120,000 ha of wetland paddy in the dry zone of Sri Lanka. Lands below the

minor tanks have been cultivated to rice only once every 5 or 6 years. Settlers harvest a successful rice crop only if wet season rainfall exceeds 1,200 mm.

New technology developed at the site has two major components — timely cultivation with the onset of wet season rainfall and a rice variety that will mature in 3-3 1/2 months. This combination allows a successful rice crop every year and the collection in tanks of runoff that is used for an additional rice

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crop or other highland crops in the dry season.

This technology has increased the paddy production in the area by a factor of 3-3 1/2 the last 5 years.

Two similar tanks in the same agro-ecological area, with and without the new technology, were compared.

The second village, Mudaperumagama, is 10-15 miles away from Walagambahuwa. Socioeconomic conditions are similar to those of Walagambahuwa. Per capita income is low and each family has 4-5 members.

Rainfall in 1980-81 was just above average:

191.8 mm in September,
212.8 in October,
460.8 in November,
108.3 in December, and
68.8 in January.

Farmers at Walagambahuwa cultivated the whole paddy under the tank with no supplementary irrigation. Average yield was 2.9 t/ha. Forty-five percent of the farmers harvested more than 3 t/ha; 28% 2-3 t/ha; and 27% less than 2 t/ha.

The farmers also saved sufficient water in the tank to use during the dry season for another rice crop or highland crops.

Farmers at Mudaperumagama started traditional paddy cultivation in late December. The crop was seeded in late January. Land preparation for paddy was by puddling, using a lot of water from the tank. The crop was raised solely with water drawn from the tank. At heading time the crop experienced moisture stress because the tank had no water for further irrigation. Forty-seven percent of the farmers harvested 0.2 t/ha and 53% 0.6-1.1 t/ha.

With the tank completely dry, there was no hope for another cultivation during the dry season. ■